

ENTREPRENEURIAL LEADERSHIP AS A CATALYST FOR THE PERFORMANCE OF SMALL AND MEDIUM SCALE ENTERPRISES IN ABIA STATE.

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Abstract: Purpose: The study addresses the lack of adequate entrepreneurial leadership among small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Abia State. It aims to investigate the influence of entrepreneurial leadership on SME performance, focusing specifically on risk-taking propensity, opportunity recognition, and proactiveness.

Methodology: A correlation research design was employed. The study population comprised 640 skilled workers from selected SMEs in Abia State. Using Krejcie and Morgan's (1970) formula, a sample size of 240 was determined. Data was collected through a validated and reliable questionnaire. Both descriptive and inferential statistics were used for data analysis, with hypotheses tested at a 5% significance level.

Findings: The analysis indicated that risk-taking propensity has a strong influence on competitiveness. Opportunity recognition was found to significantly enhance job satisfaction, while proactiveness was moderately associated with customer satisfaction but did not have a significant influence on it.

Conclusion: Entrepreneurial leadership significantly influences the performance of SMEs in Abia State. The study recommends that SMEs in Abia State should prioritize fostering a culture of risk-taking to enhance their competitive edge, as this factor has shown a significant positive impact on Competitiveness, further research should explore additional factors or external variables that might influence job satisfaction, given that opportunity recognition did not demonstrate a significant effect, businesses should consider alternative strategies to improve customer satisfaction beyond proactiveness, as this factor was not found to significantly impact satisfaction levels.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial leadership, Risk-taking propensity, Opportunity recognition, Proactiveness, Performance of small and medium scale enterprises, Competitiveness, Job satisfaction, Customer satisfaction.

Introduction

Today's global business environment has various challenges that affect the growth of SMEs; for instance, customers' changing preferences and increasing competition. These pressures make SMEs operate strategically with a focus on consumer needs as the determinants of business existence and performance (Achtenhagen, Melin & Naldi, 2018). This environment poses major challenges to SMEs since they have to constantly be on the lookout

for more efficient ways of competing efficiently. For instance, customer relationship management (CRM) systems are crucial to SMEs and help them understand patterns of customer behavior so that they can adapt the offering to the needs of the customers (Leckner et al., 2018). The rivalry forces exerted on the SMEs require response strategies that involve risk something that is driven by the entrepreneurial leadership as a crucial factor for encouraging innovation and adjustment in this segment (Rauch & Hulsink, 2018).

Entrepreneurial leadership refers to a style of leadership whereby a leader demonstrates the capacity to identify and exploit opportunities together with a risk-taking disposition. This means that through encouraging the employees to be innovative, the entrepreneurial leadership encourages the organization to progress to the next level of creativity and competitiveness (Chen, Zheng & Yang, 2020). Some of these leaders play a major role as change agents by creating an engaging culture, which allows and supports the employees to share their ideas and be innovative (Ibid). According to Urban (2020), entrepreneurial leadership is effective in SMEs since they can create sound external relationships enabling access to important resources and markets. This form of leadership is therefore directly connected to better business performance since it fosters a strong foundation of business resilience that enables SMEs to competently operate in challenging business spaces (Lee, Hallak & Sardeshmukh, 2019).

However, some unique factors prevail in the Nigerian context related to SMEs' regulatory and socio-economic challenges. In this environment, the business must be adjusted to new government policies in the country, and at the same time, the focus should be on customer satisfaction and risk management as important principles of an entrepreneurial leader (Adeola & Ezenwafor, 2020). Currently, Nigerian SMEs are adopting advanced CRM systems to develop a better capability to satisfy the customers' needs; they similarly adopt diversification strategies to avoid dependence on a single market as cited in Afolabi, Akinbinu & Sodiq, (2019). This strategic diversification coupled with the use of sustainable practices has helped Nigerian SMEs to operate legally in compliance with Environmental Laws therefore protecting and enhancing the environment have enabled the SMEs to remain relevant in both the domestic and export markets (Ademiluyi & Allan, 2021). Therefore, as Nigerian SMEs maneuver these dynamic environment factors, there is a need for entrepreneurial leadership for the promotion of innovation and sustenance of SMEs (Adegbuyi et al., 2022).

SMEs in Abia State have shifted their leadership paradigm. Traditionally, decision-making in this region was more or less the preserve of founders with strong authoritarianism. Nonetheless, the relative volatility of today's business environment is a clear indication that more collective and innovative leadership approaches are already being assumed (Okeke-Uzodike, 2021). New-generation entrepreneurs in Abia have a SOC-oriented leadership approach where team participation, customer feedback, and creativity are valued (Okoro, Nwankwo & Onyia, 2020). This change has facilitated dating and embracing new business opportunities by SMEs hence enhancing their competitiveness (Ogunnaike & Kehinde, 2020). The use of these leadership styles has also led to better

organizational performance, especially for SMEs who are more likely to embrace innovation and proactivity as a way of coping with the challenges of operating in a current business environment.

Despite the increasing interest in the adoption of a collaborative leadership approach, there is a need to analyze the extent of relevance of power-oriented leadership models in SMEs. Most founder-centered organizations continue to enjoy the personal passion and impulse-buying decisions that these leaders arrive at (Nzewi & Kelechi, 2018). Traditional entrepreneurial leaders, particularly in sectors reliant on personal networks and relationships, continue to drive business success through their deep passion and hands-on approach (Ogbuanya, 2019). Nevertheless, the evolving business landscape increasingly necessitates a shift towards more adaptable and data-driven decision-making processes (Adeola & Evans, 2022). Entrepreneurial leadership, characterized by a balance of vision, proactiveness, and calculated risk-taking, is a critical factor for the sustainable growth of SMEs in Abia and beyond (Aliyu, 2020). By blending traditional leadership strengths with new approaches, SMEs can better navigate the challenges of today's competitive global environment. Hence, this study examines entrepreneurial leadership as a catalyst for the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia State.

Objective of the Study

The broad objective of this study is to examine entrepreneurial leadership as a catalyst for the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state. Specifically, this study sought to:

1. Ascertain the influence of risk-taking propensity on the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.
2. Determine the influence of opportunity recognition on job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.
3. Determine the influence of proactiveness on customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Literature Review

Theoretical Underpinning

This study is anchored on Transformational Leadership Theory

Transformational Leadership Theory (McGregor Burns, 1978).

Transformational leadership is one of the most popular and well-researched leadership frameworks, which centers on the leader's capacity to influence the follower and produce extraordinary performance. This theory was first introduced by James MacGregor Burns in 1978 and was later improved on by Bernard M. Bass in 1985. According to Bass, transformational leadership encompasses four main components: leadership activities include providing a model that contains a positive role model, encouraging followers' behavior which contains inspiring communication, challenging creativity that contains innovative ideas, and paying attention to the needs of employees which contain personal consideration. These components establish a positive outlook of the work environment that promotes innovation and opportunities for growth of the team members (Bass, 1985).

Tenets of the theory

The leaders being in an idealized influence are expected to be role models and their followers develop trust and respect towards them (Bass, 1985). This leadership quality is important in building team loyalty and/or cohesiveness, which is important concerning organizational effectiveness (Judge & Piccolo, 2004). Through professionalism, the transformational leaders set high ethical moral standards which are emulated by the team.

Inspirational motivation can be best described as the aspect of leadership where a leader in the provision of an example, paints a picture, which the other people feel drawn to emulate. Based on Bass and Avolio's (1994) analysis, the leaders who communicate this vision help to generate such positive emotions as enthusiasm and commitment that stimulate the group's actions aimed at the achievement of the organization's objectives. They found out that this component contributes to a decrease the employee engagement and affects poor team performance (Kark et al., 2003).

Another way through which transformational leaders make changes is by stimulating ideas, a concept that goes against the norms. They give followers a reason to find unique solutions to problems and how to tackle them which makes them creative (Bass & Riggio, 2006). This type of leadership is more relevant when an organization is in a volatile environment whereby change and finding solutions to problems are essential (Eisenbeiß, van Knippenberg & Boerner, 2008).

Lastly, an individual employee's consideration entails providing him or her unique attention as well as growth opportunities in the organization. Compared to other types of leaders, transformational leaders understand the abilities and weaknesses possessed by each employee and assist them to go further to realize their potential (Bass, 1985). This aspect of leadership creates ownership of initiatives and thus makes people feel important (Eagly, Johannesen-Schmidt, & Van Engen, 2003).

Relevance of Transformational Leadership in Entrepreneurial Leadership and SMEs

Transformational leadership theory is especially relevant to entrepreneurial leadership, particularly concerning the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs). According to Avolio and Bass (1991), transformational leadership cultivates an environment conducive to innovation, risk-taking, and adaptability. Entrepreneurs, operating in highly competitive and rapidly changing markets, require leadership skills that inspire creativity and resilience. Transformational leadership provides a framework for fostering a shared sense of purpose and vision among team members, which can lead to enhanced organizational performance (Avolio & Bass, 1991). Within SMEs, transformational leaders encourage employees to engage with the organization's vision, fostering innovation and swift adaptation to market challenges (Ling, Simsek, Lubatkin, & Veiga, 2008). The individualized consideration aspect of transformational leadership ensures that employees feel supported and valued, which can increase job satisfaction and organizational commitment (Eisenbeiß et al., 2008). Moreover, transformational leadership enhances entrepreneurs' abilities to manage risks, particularly during market uncertainties (Kirkbride, 2006).

Criticisms of Transformational Leadership

While transformational leadership has gained recognition for its positive impacts on leadership effectiveness, critics argue that it may overemphasize the role of the leader and overlook contextual factors that influence leadership outcomes. According to Northouse (2018), transformational leadership may not be universally

effective in every organizational context, particularly in highly structured or bureaucratic environments where more directive leadership styles may be required.

Entrepreneurial Leadership

Leadership amongst entrepreneurs has the overall responsibility for the success and stability of organizations irrespective of their size and the type of industries they operate in from growth-stage firms to multinational companies. This form of leadership combines the best of traditional leadership practices with a focus on business-mindedness that allows leaders to seize opportunities, venture into logical risks, and promote creativity that enhances the achievement of sustainable competitive advantage (Renko et al., 2015). This is not only relevant to the start-up business champions and those who have an idea of starting new ventures but it is also applicable to already established organization managers who wish to bring the spirit of entrepreneurship within existing structures. This type of leadership is characterized by the capacity to lead employees to fulfill the objectives of an organization by properly managing opportunities and risks in the market (Leitch & Volery, 2017). Unlike other established forms of entrepreneurship that engage in the establishment of new ventures, entrepreneurial leaders consistently look for opportunities within their field and beyond creating sustainable innovations in their organizations (Bagheri, 2017). In the current environment characterized by juicy competition, organizations that foster entrepreneurial leadership stand better odds in the future than organizations that lack this culture (Fernald, Solomon, & Tarabishy, 2019).

Furthermore, it has been recently noted that entrepreneurial leadership may effectively promote entrepreneurship within the organizational setting by helping employees embrace anticipation and innovative mindsets. These attitudes are enforced by the leaders especially when they are constantly in touch with their workforce (Renko et al., 2015). This leadership approach has quickly gained popularity as organizations seek to do business in complex markets where change is almost THE norm. Entrepreneurial leadership entails communicating a vision, fear, and change as well as the control of risks, opportunities, and performance (Gupta, MacMillan, & Surie, 2018). It is more valid in SMEs because the leaders are responsible for planning and organizing resources communicating effectively with their employees and encouraging them to work hard and achieve high levels of performance despite the existing obstacles (Afsar, et al., 2021). Studies by Vecchio (2013), Chen (2017), and De Greef (2018) underscore the importance of entrepreneurial leaders in stimulating innovation and identifying hidden business opportunities, even in uncertain environments.

Performance of Small and Medium Scale Enterprises

Small and Medium-Sized Enterprises (SMEs) play a crucial role in the global economy, contributing significantly to employment, innovation, and economic growth. According to the World Bank (2021), SMEs account for around 90% of businesses worldwide, with a substantial contribution to GDP, especially in developing nations. For instance, SMEs in many Asian economies contribute up to 50% of GDP (World Bank, 2021). SMEs are also

major job creators, employing approximately 70% of the global workforce, as highlighted by the International Labor Organization (2022), which emphasizes their role in poverty alleviation and inclusive growth. Financial performance is a key indicator of SME health, and research by Zhang and Jiang (2021) shows that SMEs with strong financial management outperform their competitors and demonstrate greater resilience during economic downturns. Moreover, the capacity for innovation is a hallmark of SMEs, as their agility allows them to quickly adapt to market changes and foster technological advancements, as noted by the Schumpeter Institute (2022). However, SMEs face significant challenges, particularly in accessing finance. Ayyagari et al. (2020) emphasize that initiatives like guarantee programs and microfinance schemes have been critical in mitigating lending risks and fostering SME growth. The digital revolution has also presented both opportunities and challenges for SMEs. According to UNCTAD (2023), SMEs that embrace digital tools experience increased productivity, broader market reach, and enhanced resilience in times of disruption. Digitalization can also improve access to finance by enabling financial institutions to use data-driven fintech solutions to assess SME creditworthiness (Ayyagari et al., 2020). Furthermore, the policy environment plays an essential role in SME success. The OECD (2021) stresses the importance of favorable regulatory frameworks, streamlined registration processes, and targeted financial support for SMEs. Government interventions that foster digital transformation and provide financial assistance are crucial to enabling SMEs to thrive in an increasingly digital and competitive business landscape (OECD, 2021).

Entrepreneurial Leadership and Performance of Small and Medium-Scale Enterprises

Entrepreneurial leadership has become essential for the success and growth of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) globally. SMEs are critical drivers of economic development, employment generation, and innovation, and entrepreneurial leadership plays a pivotal role in their performance. This leadership style combines qualities such as innovation, visionary thinking, and risk-taking, empowering leaders to capitalize on emerging opportunities and guide their enterprises through volatile business environments (Renko et al., 2019). Entrepreneurial leaders are not just managers; they serve as visionaries who inspire teams, drive creativity, and encourage adaptability, which is crucial for survival in today's rapidly changing markets. Research shows that entrepreneurial leadership has a direct and positive impact on SME growth and innovation by promoting an organizational culture that embraces change and responsiveness to market dynamics (Leitch & Volery, 2017). This adaptability allows SMEs to pivot swiftly and maintain competitiveness, positioning themselves as innovative players in the global market and contributing to broader economic development.

Moreover, entrepreneurial leadership fosters a culture of creativity and risk-taking among employees, which is critical for innovation in SMEs. By cultivating an environment that encourages experimentation, entrepreneurial leaders enable the development of new products, services, and processes (Lumpkin & Dess, 2019). This emphasis on innovation is particularly crucial for SMEs, which often face significant challenges in maintaining competitiveness due to their vulnerability to market fluctuations. Entrepreneurial leaders excel in managing these

risks and adapting to new circumstances, thereby enhancing the financial performance and resilience of their businesses (Marques, 2021). Additionally, the ability of these leaders to promote a shared vision and foster a sense of ownership among employees increases motivation, productivity, and employee retention, demonstrating the far-reaching impact of entrepreneurial leadership on both organizational performance and employee satisfaction (Cardon & Kirk, 2015).

Risk-Taking Propensity and Competitiveness

Risk-taking propensity, a significant aspect of entrepreneurial leadership, plays a crucial role in shaping the competitiveness of small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). This propensity reflects an entrepreneur's willingness to engage in ventures with uncertain outcomes, often leading to innovative practices and strategic decisions that enhance the firm's market positioning. Research indicates that a higher risk-taking propensity can drive SMEs to pursue new market opportunities and adopt innovative technologies, thus improving their competitive advantage (Lussier & Halabi, 2018; Soininen et al., 2021). For instance, Kuckertz et al. (2022) found that SMEs with higher risk-taking tendencies are more likely to embrace disruptive technologies and adapt their business models, which contributes to improved performance metrics such as revenue growth and market share. Such behavior aligns with the dynamic capabilities framework, where the ability to leverage risk-taking effectively can result in superior performance outcomes (Teece et al., 2020).

However, the impact of risk-taking propensity on competitiveness is not uniformly positive. Excessive risk-taking may lead to adverse outcomes if not properly managed, potentially causing financial instability or operational challenges (Hsu et al., 2020). Balancing risk and innovation is critical, as overly aggressive strategies can undermine the stability and long-term viability of SMEs (Zahra & George, 2018). Thus, while risk-taking can stimulate competitive advantages and drive performance, it requires a strategic approach to mitigate potential downsides. Effective entrepreneurial leadership must therefore integrate risk management practices to harness the benefits of risk-taking while safeguarding against potential threats (Liu et al., 2023). Based on the above discussion, a hypothesis was developed; H_{01} : Risk-taking propensity does not have any significant influence on the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Opportunity Recognition and Job Satisfaction

Opportunity recognition is a fundamental entrepreneurial skill with a profound impact on job satisfaction and SME performance. This competency involves identifying and seizing viable business opportunities by understanding market dynamics, detecting unmet needs, and spotting emerging trends. According to Chandler (2017), opportunity recognition is not merely about passive observation but an active process that fosters innovation and sustainable competitive advantage. Entrepreneurs who excel in this area can better navigate the evolving business landscape, position their SMEs for growth, and enhance their competitive edge. The ability to recognize and act upon these opportunities significantly contributes to the creation of a stimulating work environment, which, in turn, enhances job satisfaction among employees (Chandler, 2017).

Job satisfaction is crucial to the performance and competitiveness of SMEs. Employees who feel content with their work are more motivated, committed, and productive, leading to improved overall business success (Chandler, 2017). Entrepreneurs who are adept at opportunity recognition often introduce innovative products or services, which can create a dynamic work environment conducive to higher job satisfaction (Amabile, 2023). Furthermore, the growth spurred by effective opportunity capture provides employees with career advancement opportunities, enhancing their job satisfaction (Van der Sluis, Van Praag, & Vijverberg, 2018). Involvement in decision-making and the autonomy granted by opportunity-oriented entrepreneurs further boost employee satisfaction (Hackman & Oldham, 2020). Empirical studies support this connection, with research indicating that SMEs led by entrepreneurs with strong opportunity recognition skills tend to have more satisfied employees (Cardon, Stevens, & Potter, 2012; Leitch & Harrison, 2016). Based on the above discussion, a hypothesis was developed; H₀₂: Opportunity recognition does not have a significant influence on job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Proactiveness and Customer Satisfaction

Proactiveness in entrepreneurial leadership is a key attribute that enables leaders to anticipate and act on future developments, positioning their businesses ahead of competitors. This forward-thinking approach fosters innovation, helping organizations identify niche markets and unmet customer needs. According to Kovačič and Virant (2020), proactive leaders exhibit strong trend-spotting and strategic planning abilities, which are crucial for maintaining a competitive edge. In Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs), this proactiveness allows leaders to develop tailored offerings that enhance customer satisfaction, leading to increased loyalty and a positive reputation. SMEs that excel in customer satisfaction are more likely to retain customers and gain word-of-mouth referrals, crucial for long-term profitability and growth (Brodie, 2019).

Customer satisfaction, in turn, directly contributes to the success and sustainability of SMEs. Satisfied customers tend to exhibit loyalty and recommend the business to others, which strengthens the brand reputation and attracts new customers (Barger & Grandey, 2020). High customer satisfaction also leads to operational efficiency, as fewer complaints and returns result in cost savings (Yang et al., 2022). Proactive leaders in SMEs play a vital role in fostering this satisfaction by anticipating customer needs and addressing potential issues before they arise. As Fernandes and Albuquerque (2021) note, proactive leadership cultivates a culture of continuous improvement, where innovation is encouraged, further enhancing the customer experience. This proactive focus on customer needs not only boosts satisfaction but also drives business growth, making proactiveness an indispensable trait of successful entrepreneurial leadership in SMEs. Based on the above discussion, a hypothesis was developed; H₀₃ Proactiveness does not have any significant influence on customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Gap in Literature

The existing empirical literature on entrepreneurial leadership and SME performance predominantly covers various international and Nigerian contexts, focusing mainly on SMEs in the South-South, South-Western, and North-Eastern regions of Nigeria. However, a significant gap exists in research concerning the Eastern region, particularly Abia State. The literature reveals a lack of studies addressing entrepreneurial leadership dimensions such as risk-taking propensity, opportunity recognition, and proactiveness, as well as performance metrics like profitability, productivity, and customer satisfaction within this region. This gap highlights the need for comprehensive research in Abia State to enhance understanding and provide valuable insights into the specific dynamics of entrepreneurial leadership and SME performance in this underserved geographical area.

Methodology

The research methodology is meticulously outlined, detailing the procedures and techniques employed for this study. The research adopted a correlation design to explore the relationships between entrepreneurial leadership and SME performance, in line with Boucaud's (2017) and Tsetim et al.'s (2020) recommendations for investigating variable connections. The study was conducted in selected SMEs within the manufacturing sector in Abia State, Nigeria, known for its vibrant economic activities and high population density, especially in urban centers like Aba. The target population comprised 640 skilled workers from various SMEs, and a sample size of 240 was determined using Krejcie and Morgan's formula (1970), ensuring statistical reliability. Stratified sampling, as described by Bowley's method, allocated the sample proportionally across different enterprises to maintain representativeness. Primary data were collected via a structured questionnaire, specifically designed to assess entrepreneurial leadership and employee performance. This questionnaire, divided into two sections—one addressing socio-demographic information and the other focusing on research-specific variables—was validated through both face and content validity methods, and its reliability was confirmed via a pilot test with a Cronbach alpha coefficient of 0.763 for the leadership instrument and 0.848 for the performance instrument. Data collection involved the personal distribution of the questionnaires to ensure accuracy and completeness. The collected data were analyzed using descriptive statistics and linear regression to assess the impact of leadership on SME performance. Descriptive statistics provided insights into respondents' demographics, while linear regression analysis measured the strength of relationships and tested hypotheses at a 0.05 alpha level using SPSS version 24. The decision rule stipulated that hypotheses would be accepted or rejected based on p-values, with a p-value ≤ 0.05 indicating rejection of the null hypothesis. This comprehensive methodology ensures robust and reliable findings aligned with the study's objectives.

Results

Hypothesis 1

Risk-taking propensity does not have any significant influence on the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state

Table 1: Simple regression analysis on risk-propensity significantly influencing the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises

Model	R	R Square	Change Statistics
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			Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change	Square F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.770 ^a	.593	.567	12.63073	.000	5.791	1	239	.000	

a. Predictors: (Constant), risk-taking propensity

The analysis in Table 1 reveals the linear regression analysis on risk propensity not significantly influencing the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises. At 0.05 alpha level, $t_{(1,239)} = 5.791$, $p = 0.000$, the null hypothesis is rejected. The null hypothesis is rejected because the sig. A value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 alpha level, therefore, risk-taking propensity significantly influenced the competitiveness of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state

Hypothesis 2

Opportunity recognition does not have a significant influence on the job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Table 2: Simple regression analysis on opportunity recognition significantly influencing job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises

					Change Statistics					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change	Square F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.821 ^a	.674	.663	12.60478	.005	.502	1	239	.000	

a. Predictors: (Constant), opportunity recognition

The analysis in Table 2 reveals the linear regression analysis on opportunity recognition does not have a significant influence on job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state. At 0.05 alpha level, $t_{(1,239)} = .502$, $p = 0.000$, the null hypothesis is rejected. The null hypothesis is rejected because the sig. A value of 0.000 is less than 0.05 alpha level, therefore, opportunity recognition significantly influences on job satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Hypothesis 3

Proactiveness does not have any significant influence on customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Table 3: Simple regression analysis on proactiveness not significantly influencing customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises

Model Summary

					Change Statistics					
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted Square	RStd. Error of the Estimate	Change	Square F Change	df1	df2	Sig. Change	F
1	.546 ^a	.298	.271	12.60478	.002	.190	1	239	.456	

a. Predictors: (Constant), Proactiveness

The analysis in Table 3 reveals the linear regression analysis on proactiveness does not have a significant influence on customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia State. At 0.05 alpha level, $t_{(1,239)} = 0.190$, $p = 0.456$, the null hypothesis is not rejected. The null hypothesis is not rejected because the sig. A value

of 0.456 is greater than 0.05 alpha level, therefore, proactiveness does not have any significant influence on customer satisfaction of small and medium-scale enterprises in Abia state.

Conclusion and Recommendations

In conclusion, the study highlights the crucial role of entrepreneurial leadership in driving the performance of small and medium-scale enterprises (SMEs) in Abia State. Entrepreneurial leaders, characterized by innovation and proactive decision-making, foster a culture of creativity and adaptability, leading to enhanced organizational performance, employee engagement, and customer satisfaction. However, the success of entrepreneurial leadership depends on access to resources and a supportive business environment. Therefore, stakeholders should prioritize initiatives that develop entrepreneurial skills and create a conducive environment for SMEs to thrive, addressing challenges such as limited access to finance and inadequate infrastructure, to enable sustainable growth and performance.

Sequel to the findings and conclusion, the study advocates as following:

1. SMEs in Abia State should prioritize fostering a culture of risk-taking to enhance their competitive edge, as this factor has shown a significant positive impact on competitiveness.
2. Further research should explore additional factors or external variables that might influence job satisfaction, given that opportunity recognition did not demonstrate a significant effect.
3. Businesses should consider alternative strategies to improve customer satisfaction beyond proactiveness, as this factor was not found to significantly impact satisfaction levels.

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